

THE FEATURES OF ENGLISH-UZBEK MILITARY PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abdullayeva Sanobar Xamzayevna

A teacher of the Academy Of MIA

Abstract: *The features and analysis of the military specific phraseological units in the English language provides the classification of phraseological units by structural and semantic principle in nominative (substantive, adjective, adverbial and prepositional), nominative-communicative (verbal), interjectional and modal uninterjectional, and communicative phraseologisms; identifies basic semantic groups such as designation of the various military service phenomena, armaments and military equipment, the activities during the hostilities and exercises, personnel daily routine. The article concludes that most of the military specific phraseological units are idiomatic and phraseomatic word-combinations relating to substantive and verbal phraseologisms according to their structural and semantic features; modal and interjectional phraseological units are represented in less degree.*

Keywords: *phraseologism, phraseological unit, idiom, military, classification, semantic group.*

The study of the phraseological fund, which is a kind of reflection of the picture of the world of native speakers, the spirit and culture of the people, is becoming increasingly relevant.

The isolation of combinations of words reproduced in the language in a finished form was initially necessary to separate fixed phrases from combinations that naturally and regularly form in speech. In the "Course of General Linguistics," F. de Saussure noted that in the language there are a large number of expressions that are ready-made statements, the composition of which cannot be changed even if they can be decomposed into meaningful parts. Such expressions, according to the theory of the linguist, exist in the language in finished form and are transmitted according to tradition.

To understand the term "phraseology", we consider it appropriate to reveal the content side of this concept. Phraseological units as an object of study of the science of phraseology are semantically related words and sentences, which "unlike syntactic structures similar to them in form, are not

produced in accordance with the general patterns of choice and combination of words when organizing an utterance, but are reproduced in a speech in a fixed ratio of the semantic structure and a certain lexical and grammatical composition "

One of the richest resources of phraseological units in the language is professional speech. Terminological vocabulary easily acquires a figurative meaning due to figurative and metaphorical use, gradually moving into the category of phraseological units with their characteristic features and properties. Phraseological units used in a speech by a certain professional group often pass into the category of commonly used ones.

Within the framework of this article, we will focus on the phraseological units of the military sphere, from which a large number of set expressions were borrowed, which subsequently received a new rethought meaning.

The fund of phraseological units of the military theme of the English language is very extensive, in this regard, we will consider the classification of phraseological units of this type according to the principle proposed by A.V. Kunin, who divided phraseology into idiomatic, idiophraseomatics, and phraseomatics.

The first section, idioms, includes phraseological units (idioms) - stable combinations of words, the meaning of which is completely or partially rethought. Among them stand out:

- nominative, including substantive, adjective, adverbial and prepositional phraseological units;
- nominative and nominative-communicative phraseological units, consisting of verbal phraseological units;
- interjectional phraseological units and modal phraseological units of a non-interjective nature;
- communicative phraseological units (proverbs and sayings)

The first class of nominative idioms includes substantive phraseological units of the military sphere, which are a large layer of phraseological units and fusions. They serve to designate an object and correlate, based on the functions performed, with nouns that are their main element, that is, a grammatically independent component that is related to a certain part of speech and explains the functioning of a phraseological unit in the form of a word class. Substantive phraseological units are formed by either complete (metaphorical or metonymic) or incomplete rethinking. Metaphorically rethought phraseological units are understood as phrases that have arisen on the basis of similarity with any object or phenomenon.

Such phraseological units serve to designate and evaluate, for example, persons: *companion (comrade) in arms* - quoldosh (o'rtoq), *a red coat* - ingliz askari. An assessment can be expressed explicitly, which implies the presence of an evaluative word directly in the PU (for example, the expression *an awkward squad* - yollanma vzvod, "qo'pol vzvod) and implicitly. An implication is a meaning that is guessed by the carrier, but not verbally expressed. Substantive phraseological units often have a connotation of evaluation, which can be both positive and negative: an old campaigner is *tajribali jangchi*", *colonel Chinstrap* - "Polkovnik Chinstrap" - quvnoq odam, ichkilikboz, *big gun* - muhim shaxs; *big brass* - generallar, generallar, yuqori martabali harbiylar, *colonel Blimp* - "Polkovnik Blimp" - inertsiya, o'jarlik, konservatizm timsoli.

Some phraseological units that serve to designate persons do not carry any assessment, they are neutral: *brother in arms* - quoldosh askar, *a blue coat* - askar, dengizchi, *a brass hat* - bosh ofitser.

Among the substantive military idioms denoting an inanimate object, there are also phraseological units with a positive, negative and neutral assessment. For example, *the dogs of war* - urush dahshatlari, urush kuchlari, *a call to arms* - xizmatga chorlov

Adjective phraseological units have the meaning of a qualitative characteristic and, like adjectives, in a sentence defines as in the function of defining or nominal part of the predicate. Among the adjective phraseological units of military subjects, the following phraseological units are:

quick on the trigger - hozirjavob, epchil;

armed to the teeth - o'ta qurollangan;

camp happy - aqldan ozgan;

low on amps and voltage - tashabbusning etishmasligi.

Adverbial and prepositional phraseological units include qualitative adverbial and adverbial phraseological units. Qualitative adverbial phraseological units are stable phrases denoting the quality of an object. Circumstantial adverbial phraseological units describe the conditions under which the process takes place:

with flying colors - g'olib;

on the alert - shay, ogoh;

without (striking) a blow - jangsiz;

up in arms - jang qilish, qarshilik ko'rsatishga tayyor; biror narsaga keskin e'tiroz bildirish, norozilik bildirish; biror narsaga yoki kimgadir qarshi qurol olish;

above the battle - jangdan uzoqda;;

with the colors - amaldagi xizmatda, armiyada

Prepositional phraseological units serve to link components in a sentence: *in force* - asosiy kuchlar.

The second class includes verbal phraseological units - phraseological units with the meaning of action, process. To systematize the verbal idioms of military subjects, it seems appropriate to describe the semantic groups of words. This definition refers to a number of words or phrases that are close in basic meaning, that is, belonging to the same semantic field. As a rule, such associations of words are characterized by a common lexical meaning and formation into groups based on the concepts embedded in them.

We assigned phraseological units to the first semantic group, denoting the beginning of certain actions, the readiness to start doing things:

fly to arms - shoshilinch ravishda urushga tayyorgarlik ko'rish, qurol ko'tarish;

rise in (take up) arms (against) - qo'lga olmoq, jang qilmoq (qarshilik qilmoq);

join battle - muzokara boshlash yoki aksincha;

clear the decks - jangga, jangga tayyorgarlik ko'ring

dig up the hatchet (tomahawk) - urush boshlash.

The following group of verbal phraseological units describes the nature of the struggle, it can represent both positive actions and deception, and hostility:

change one's battery - to'g'ridan-to'g'ri boshqa tomonga o't oching, taktikani o'zgartiring

mask one's batteries - dushmanlik niyatlarini yashirish;

turn smb.'s battery against himself - dushmanni o'z quroli bilan urmoq;

fling (throw) oneself into the breach - muammodan xalos bo'lish, yordamga kelish.

In a separate semantic group, verbal phraseological units denoting success, victory in a certain business should be distinguished:

carry the day - kurashda, jangda, g'alaba qozonish;

save the day - muvaffaqiyatsiz boshlangan jangni muvaffaqiyatli yakunlamoq;

show fight - jangga tayyor bo'l, jangari bo'l, taslim bo'lma;;

And, conversely, a number of verb phraseological units mean failure, collapse, defeat as in the following:

lay down one's arms - taslim bo'lish;

throw down one's arms - taslim bo'lmoq;

fight a losing battle - samarasiz kurash olib bormoq

leave smb. in possession of the field - mag'lub bo'lish.

The third class includes interjectional phraseological units (*bless my life! My eyes!*) and modal phraseological units of a non-interjective nature (*well and good, not at all*). Interjectional phraseological units are stable combinations that serve to express emotions and feelings, modal phraseological units characterize the speaker's attitude to the topic of the statement. An example of phraseological units of military subjects in this class can be the expressions *all clear* - havo hujumi bartaraf etildi, *as straight as an arrow* - o'qdek tez.

The fourth class includes communicative phraseological units, that is, proverbs and sayings:

attack is the best method of defense - eng yaxshi himoya hujumdir;

come unscathed out of the battle - suvdan quruq chiqmoq;

a threatened blow is seldom given - tez-tez tahdid qilinadigan zarba kamdan-kam hollarda beriladi;

every bullet has its billet – taqdirdan qochib bo'lmaydi;

forewarned, forarmed – ogohlik-shaylik.

The section of idio-phraseomatics consists of stable phrases that have both literal and rethought meanings. The first meaning of a phraseological unit of this type, as a rule, is a professionalism or a term, the second is a rethought version of the main meaning.

Among the substantive idiophraseological units, the following can be distinguished:

the rank and file - 1) saf qism; 2) safdorlar;

a running fire - 1) otilgan o'q; 2) tanqidiy fikr-mulohazalar;

the seat of war - 1) urush joyi; 2) urush o'chog'i.

A large group is formed by verbal idiophraseomatisms:

stand fire - 1) bardosh berish; 2) qarshilik qilish;

return to the charge - 1) harbiy hujumni davom ettirish; 2) muhokamani, bahsni davom ettirish

take the field against - 1) harbiy harakatlarni boshlash; 2) qarshilik qilish;;

turn the flank of smb. (smth.) - 1) aylanib o'tish

take by storm - 1) ommaviy qo'lga olish;

mark time - 1) harbiy yurish; 2) turg'unlik, hech narsa qilmaslik.

Among military idio-phraseomatisms there are adverbial and adjective phraseological units, for example:

under fire - 1) dushman zarbasi ostida; 2) hujumlar ostida;;

with a rush - 1) tezda; 2) tez;;

on parole – 1)harbiy jangovar harakatlarda qatnashmaslik majburiyatini olish (mahbus haqida); 2) shartli ravishda ozod qilingan.

The third section, phraseomatics, includes phrases that are not formally stable, but have a complicated meaning. "Such phrases, on the one hand, are reproducible units of the language, and on the other hand, they are formed according to the generative model of a variable phrase, i.e. are variable-stable formations"

In the composition of phraseological turns of military subjects, we single out, firstly, a semantic group that includes various types of weapons:

to detonate (explode, set off) a bomb - bomba tashlamoq

to drop a bomb - bomba tashlamoq;

to fire a weapon – o't ochmoq;

to handle a weapon – qurol ishlatish;

to lay (throw down) one's weapons - harbiy harakatlardan bosh tortish; taslim bo'lish;

to load a weapon – qurolni quvvatlash.

The second group includes the actions of military personnel during military operations, exercises:

bloody battle - qonli jang; *decisive battle* – hal qiluvchi jang; *fierce (raging) battle* - shiddatli jang; *losing battle* - jangda mag'lub bo'lish; *to do (give) battle* - jang qilmoq; *to join battle* – jangga kirishmoq; *to fight (wage) battle* - jang qilmoq *terminate a battle* – jangni to'xtatmoq, *line of defense* - mudofaa; *to conduct (organize, put up) a defense* - himoya qilish; *to overwhelm smb.'s defenses* – himoyani yorib o'tmoq; *to fight to the finish* – oxirigacha jang qilish; *to fight a battle* - jang bermoq; *to achieve peace* – tinchlikka erishish; *durable (lasting) peace* - mustahkam tinchlik; *fragile peace*- qisqa muddatli tinchlik, *to hold smb. (as a) hostage* – garovga olmoq; *to seize (take) smb. hostage* - kimnidir qo'lga olish. garovga olingan; *to carry out an invasion* - bosqinni qaytarmoq

The third group includes military-themed phraseomatisms that describe the daily activities and life of military personnel:

direct order - to'g'ridan-to'g'ri buyurtma; *to give an order* – buyruq berish; *to carry out (execute) an order* - buyruqni bajarish; *to obey (follow) orders* – buyruqqa bo'ysunish; *to cancel (rescind, revoke) an order* - buyurtmani bekor qilish, *to violate an order* - tartibni buzish; *to break (demote, dismiss) an officer* - ofitserni lavozimidan ozod etish, ishdan bo'shatish; *to commission an officer* – lavozimga tayinlash; *to promote an officer* - unvonini oshirish.

As a result of the analysis of phraseological units of military subjects, we have formulated the following conclusions:

1. The fund of military phraseological units is a vast layer of idioms, idiophraseomatisms and phraseomatisms with the prevalence of the first and third ones.

2. Idiomatic and idio-phraseological turns of military subjects - a large group of phraseological units, most of which, according to their structural and semantic features, belong to substantive and verbal phraseological units, which are the most productive set expressions in any language; to a lesser extent, modal and interjectional phraseological units are represented in the military sphere, which is explained by the general nature of their use.

3. Phraseomatics of the military sphere includes phrases that serve to denote various phenomena of military service, weapons and military equipment, activities during hostilities and exercises, and the daily life of military personnel.

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